

COMPETENT LEVELS OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE APPLICATION OF VIRTUAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

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Annotation. The article discusses measures to prevent students from teaching students on the use of virtual educational technologies, conditions and circumstances in the pedagogical character, which may occur in this process and the negative consequences.

Keywords: Education, pedagogical training, virtual education, information, education, information systems, information systems, information systems, information systems, electronic teaching aids.

Introduction. Specialization of the contents of the contents of the content of the training of future teachers on the use of virtual teachers in the process of taking advantage of virtual teachers in the process of using virtual learning technology, the specialty of primary education and sports work We will focus on the description of the preparation of students for professional practice.

The first direction of the training content provides key characteristics of the global mass communication communication and reveals the impact of education in the development aspect of informational information. The capabilities of virtual educational technologies and their role in improving modern education is of particular importance.

Literature review. The concept of informational society is based on the content and characteristics of the modern society, the mass communications and globalization, and is formed with relying on it. The virtual technology tools make use of all types of education, scientific, leisure, professional, free time, and daily activities. The concept of informatization is described as a socio-economic process, which covers all sectors of the modern society. Its most common type is the activities of mutual information in everyday life and use of information.

The content of the idea of informatization of education is the process of developing the theory and methods of using virtual education technologies, while the development of virtual educational technologies unites the results of pedagogical, psychological and technological research. viewed as an scientific field.

The interaction of information in the definitions of virtual educational technologies, the impact of information, described information processes, and their place in the development of education is opened.

Scientific novelty of the article. Educational, processing, storage, transmission, demonstration, production, production, production, production, production of information entities There are various forms of organization and implementation of information activity.

Information provided by virtual education technologies, processing, administration and receiving, reflected, interactive communication, text, graphical, animation, audio and video data viewed as an exchange process. The structure of information interactions is considered an internal form of organization of information exchanges in the middle of the interactive source of educators, students and virtual information.

Didactic opportunities for virtual educational technologies: In response to any student's request, visual interaction that determines the implementation of an interactive conversation; visualization of learning information on the screen, study information on processes; Save any amounts of information with easy access, transmitting it, repeating it; Automation of information activities with data collection, processing, transmitting, copying, surprisingly large data in the archive and access to it; Information and methodological processes Automate, organizational management and assimilation of the results of educational activities are opened.

Analysis and results. The purposefulness of the use of virtual educational technologies is reflected in:

- Development of the student, its mass media and the globalization for prosperous information society in the modern information society;
- Improving processes in working with virtual technology tools, automation of management processes, improving the educational processing information Internet search, using interactive board, and use of graphs;
- Globalization and social order in the context of the Information Society.

The circumstances that may occur in the pedagogical description are:

- Structure, quality, content of the information, content, awareness of the student and the compliance or inconsistency in terms of its level of preparation;
- use of unacceptable volume data, its content and methodological purpose;
- The student's full perception is revealed to its age characteristics and the causes of the negative consequences that have a medical character;

- Term of staying in computer games, including network games, interviews, etc., "virtual reality" of the student;
- Violation of the student ergonomics equipped with virtual technologies of the workplace;
- Mass Information Communication and Globalization Information Society in case of risks and problems with virtual technologies emerging with virtual technologies, which occur with the means of operation, not match the approved documentation.

Measures to prevent the possible negative consequences in pedagogical and medical descriptions include:

- Providing information depending on the young characteristics of the student on the screen;
- submission to the content of the data and according to methodical and according to the student's level of preparation;
- the ability of the student and the use of time interval that meets its level of preparation;
- The need to adapt the requirements for virtual communities on social media;
- The need to protect students to computer games, including network games.
- It is necessary to form a positive "self-representing" in contact with information with information on the Internet, including information in network communities;
- To emphasize the need to form a healthy lifestyle for the student in the Global Sector Communications Information Society, attention to the coordination.

The information and learning resource for primary schools is the emergence of information effects on educational influence using interactive virtual technology tools and Definition of a favorable conditions for the development.

The composition of objects of information and educational institutions of primary schools is as follows: software and technical means and information systems, information networks; Educational-methodical developments and organizational materials of the education system provided in electronic form is characterized by information educational resources for primary schools.

The performance of a Virtual information learning environment relies on the interaction of users between themselves, with objects as well as on-screen images.

The structure of the virtual information education environment of primary classes wished to present as the content of components that demonstrate the conditions for the implementation of information and educational interaction between the student, teacher and information education resources using interactive tools of virtual technologies. The directions of information flows are indicated either directly or interrelated from the teacher to the students, as well as directly or interrelated in the interactive information resource.

Thus, we can generalize the above and draw the following conclusions.

Conclusion. The components of information and educational impacts is the resource of both educational processes and interactive individuals or interactive information of virtual technologies. The exchange of mutual information between teachers, students or students and interactive electronic information education - will be provided directly or interactive.

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